

June, 2025

RDA and Microsoft White Paper

Data Readiness and Data-Centric AI

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Based on the RDA-Microsoft roundtables in May 2025

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1. Executive Summary

Artificial Intelligence (AI), powered by data, is rapidly transforming research by accelerating discovery, reshaping methods, and redefining collaboration. Recognising both its promise and challenges, the **Research Data Alliance (RDA)** and **Microsoft** convened two global roundtables in May 2025. These virtual global events featured keynotes and breakout sessions with participants from across **six** continents on three core themes: **Data Readiness for AI, AI in Research, and AI Governance.**

Global data and AI experts provided insights into AI in research and practice through their impactful **keynote speeches**. Through **moderated, interactive discussions**, participants highlighted challenges such as gaps in metadata standards, data quality, and limited automation tools. They stressed the need to improve reproducibility, strengthen documentation, and confront ethical issues linked to biased, Anglo-centric datasets. Discussions also underscored the evolving role of researchers, emphasising the importance of human agency and expertise. A common priority was establishing harmonised governance frameworks for responsible, ethical AI use.

Findings and Recommendations:

- Develop **interdisciplinary AI training programmes** to build in-demand skills such as prompt engineering, agentic AI, data preparation, and ethical reasoning.
- Establish clear **institutional and publishing guidelines for responsible AI use**, transparency, and reproducibility.
- Advocate for **human-centred AI** strategies to reinforce researcher agency, ensure equitable access, and mitigate automation risks.
- Invest in **automated data preparation tools, robust metadata standards**, and dedicated stewardship roles to enhance data readiness.
- Support **smaller, domain-specific AI models** with curated datasets to foster inclusivity, reduce environmental impacts, and improve adaptability.
- Expand **secure, privacy-preserving infrastructures** such as Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and regulatory sandboxes.
- Mandate rigorous **reproducibility practices, transparent dataset bias disclosures**, and clear authorship guidelines for AI-generated outputs.
- Enhance **global regulatory collaboration** and adopt harmonised frameworks like the EU AI Act and UNESCO guidelines.

We believe that these findings and recommendations offer strategic guidance for researchers, academic institutions, policymakers, research funders, and technology stakeholders, ensuring responsible and inclusive AI integration with strong data foundations into global research efforts.

2. Introduction & Background

Rapidly advancing technologies, notably Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Quantum Computing, are significantly impacting the landscape of scientific research. From reducing chemical discovery timelines (from several months down to approximately 200 hours¹) to accelerating the understanding of protein structures (an advancement recognised²), the impact and potential of these technologies is immense³.

In recognition of these advancements and their implications, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and Microsoft jointly organised a series of expert roundtables in May and June 2025. These roundtables aimed to stimulate global community dialogue, foster meaningful discussions, and identify practical frameworks and best practices for responsible advancement in the impactful fields of AI and Quantum Computing.

The two main themes of the roundtables were:

1. "Data Readiness and Data-Centric AI Skills." (2025, 13 and 15 May)
2. "From HPC to Quantum – Shaping the Future of Research Computing" (2025, 3 and 5 June))

The roundtables were structured to maximise global engagement and inclusive dialogue. Sessions were scheduled to accommodate participants across diverse time zones, ensuring broad international participation. The tangible outcomes of these sessions are two whitepapers, one per theme, made openly available to the global research community in July 2025. This white paper synthesises findings specifically from the two sessions that concentrated on "Data Readiness and Data-Centric AI Skills."

To gather valuable insights for the roundtables RDA leveraged its position as an inclusive and open discussion platform, with a global community presence across all continents, and extensive experience in data driven innovation. Concurrently, Microsoft contributed its expansive technological expertise, and its technology driven global research

¹<https://news.microsoft.com/source/features/innovation/how-ai-and-hpc-are-speeding-up-scientific-discovery/>

² <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/chemistry/2024/popular-information/>

³ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-025-00343-5>

initiatives. In April 2025 Microsoft joined the RDA as an organisational member. You can consult the organisational profiles of the RDA and Microsoft at the end of [Section 6](#) of this document. Invited attendees at the roundtables included leading researchers, policymakers, funders, data stewards, technologists, and industry leaders. By engaging both public and private sector partners, these dialogues aimed to foster a constructive discussion among stakeholders who are driving the advancements and usage of these technologies. Each session featured expert keynote presentations followed by structured breakout discussions. Interactive tools and platforms were utilised to facilitate real-time engagement and idea exchange, further enriching the collaborative experience. The insights presented in this white paper directly reflect participant inputs, moderator discussions, and thematic analyses conducted throughout the sessions.

2.1 Data Readiness and Data-Centric AI: Rationale and Global Stakeholder Input

The themes of Data Readiness and Data-Centric AI for the 2025 May roundtables were carefully selected due to their foundational role in realising the transformative potential of AI. High-quality, well-managed data is crucial for accurate, reproducible, and robust AI-driven insights⁴. Rapid technological progress places unprecedented demands on data infrastructure, data governance, and skilled personnel capable of managing these advanced methodologies⁵. Therefore, addressing data readiness and skill development emerged as key priorities that align closely with the practical needs and strategic interests of both the research community and technology providers⁶.

⁴ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/ful/10.1145/3722214>

⁵ <https://epubs.siam.org/doi/10.1137/1.9781611977653.ch106>

⁶ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12599-024-00857-8>

Figure 1: Top discussion themes preferences of the participants at the time of registration across both roundtables.

To ensure the alignment of the roundtables to research community needs, global stakeholder input was actively sought prior to the events. During the registration process, 135 global stakeholders from RDA and Microsoft were invited to specify their top 3 thematic interests and concerns. This engagement strategy helped identify three thematic areas- **Data Readiness for AI**, **AI in Research** and **AI Governance**, as shown in Figure 1. This feedback was instrumental in shaping the roundtable agenda, ensuring that discussions directly addressed the most pressing challenges and opportunities identified by the global research and technology community.

2.2 Participant Profiles and AI Experience

The RDA–Microsoft roundtables on Data and AI attracted a globally representative and highly diverse group of stakeholders from **20 countries across six continents**. Participation spanned countries including **Australia, United States, Canada, Italy, United Kingdom, Netherlands, India, Singapore, New Zealand, Costa Rica, Ethiopia, Norway, Sweden, France, Belgium, Ireland, Denmark, Germany, United Arab Emirates, and South Korea**, underscoring the broad appeal and relevance of the themes explored.

Stakeholders included academic researchers from prominent universities, policy experts from government agencies, data stewards from international repositories, technologists from private sector organisations, and infrastructure leaders from global research networks. Contributing participants of the roundtables are listed in [Appendix B](#). We thank them for their enthusiastic engagement and impactful insights during the roundtables.

Figure 2: AI experience levels of the participants (Mentimeter poll)

As shown in Figure 2, Participants' AI expertise was wide-ranging, with experience roughly divided between those identifying as beginners who had used basic AI tools, and those engaged in more advanced activities such as developing models or leading institutional AI strategy. An additional group of 15 respondents across both roundtables selected “unsure” and are not represented in the figure.

Building on this diverse range of expertise and perspectives, the structure of this white paper reflects the roundtable format and areas of participant focus. Beginning with key insights from invited keynote speakers who provided strategic and technical framing for the discussions, this paper will then present a synthesis of the participant discussion, which explored three core themes: **Data Readiness for AI, AI in Research, and AI Governance**. To conclude, a summary of collective findings, practical recommendations, and next steps is presented, informed by keynotes, participant contributions, live polling, and moderated discussion.

3. Global Thought Leadership: Expert Keynotes and Audience Discussions

This section summarises the keynote speeches delivered by global experts during the RDA–Microsoft roundtables on Data readiness and Data-centric AI skills. It captures the core messages from each speaker along with highlights from the audience Q&A that followed. Detailed profiles of all keynote speakers are provided in [Appendix A](#).

3.1 Ensuring Responsible AI Readiness with a Sandbox Approach: Arnaud Ceol

Speaker: Arnaud Ceol, Technical Project Manager, National Research Centre for High Performance Computing, Big Data and Quantum Computing (ICSC⁷), **Italy**, 2025, May 13

Arnaud Ceol’s keynote explored how the European Union is navigating a core tension in its AI policy. On one hand, the goal is to advance AI innovation and adoption, particularly among research institutions and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). On the other, it is to ensure that AI systems remain legally compliant, ethically grounded, and aligned with fundamental rights. Representing ICSC and an EU funded project EUSAiR⁸, Arnaud presented AI regulatory sandboxes as a practical mechanism to help operationalise this policy agenda, particularly as the European Union (EU) AI Act⁹ enters into force.

The EU AI Act is the world’s first comprehensive legal framework for artificial intelligence (law since Aug 2024, fully operational in August 2026). It takes a risk-based approach, categorising AI systems into four levels: unacceptable, high, limited, and minimal risk. High-risk systems, such as those used in healthcare, education, or public administration, must meet stringent requirements around transparency, human oversight, bias mitigation, and data governance to be deployed lawfully in the EU.

To support compliance without stifling innovation, Arnaud introduced the regulatory sandbox as a structured environment where developers can test and validate AI systems under expert supervision. Sandboxes offer legal and technical scaffolding for AI development, enabling teams to engage with governance expectations early, rather than

⁷ <https://www.supercomputing-icsc.it/en/icsc-home/>

⁸ <https://eusair-project.eu/>

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1689>

retrofitting them at deployment. These environments are particularly relevant to smaller institutions or public-sector teams that may lack in-house regulatory capacity.

Arnaud highlighted the EUSAIR Sandbox Pilot¹⁰, a public–private initiative coordinated by ICSC, and the University of Bologna and involving, among others, partners in Italy, Spain, and Finland, as a practical example of this approach. Crucially, Arnaud underscored that data readiness is now a compliance issue. Under the AI Act, training data must be “representative, complete, and statistically appropriate”, especially in sensitive or public-facing domains. Sandboxes help lower the entry barrier by embedding compliance into the development workflow itself.

Quoting the early application in the financial technology (fintech) sector, Arnaud noted that regulatory sandboxes can accelerate both trust and deployment. Firms using sandbox pathways saw sixfold increases in investment and brought products to market 40% faster than peers operating outside regulated environments.

“The sandbox isn’t just infrastructure. It’s a Data and AI governance tool that helps institutions move from principle to practice on Trustworthy AI.”

- Arnaud Ceol

Audience Q&A with Arnaud Ceol: Highlights

Following the presentation, participants raised several implementation-oriented questions:

- **On HPC infrastructure access to low- and middle-income countries**, Arnaud clarified that while the EU-AI factory¹¹ infrastructure is EU-funded and accessible for European users especially SMEs and startups, the sandbox framework is portable. Equivalent models could be deployed in compliant cloud environments (such as Microsoft Azure), assuming security and governance standards are met.
- **On project eligibility**, he explained that sandboxes are selective and time bound. Only well-scoped, mature projects are admitted, typically for six-month cycles, with governance experts guiding validation throughout.
- **On the relationship to Trusted Research Environments (TREs¹²)**, Arnaud distinguished sandboxes as spaces for AI model validation and risk management

¹⁰ <https://eusair-project.eu/>

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-factories>

¹² <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

under regulatory supervision, whereas TREs are primarily designed for secure data access and privacy-preserving research.

In closing, Arnaud noted that every EU member state will be required to implement at least one regulatory sandbox by the end of 2026. He invited researchers, developers, and data stewards to begin engaging now: by evaluating their AI workflows, participating in sandbox pilots, and embedding compliance readiness at the infrastructure level.

3.2 Data-Centric GenAI for Healthcare: From Infrastructure to Impact: Harshad Keskar

Speaker: Harshad Keskar, Data and AI Evangelist (Higher Education), Microsoft, London, United Kingdom, 2025, May 13

Harshad Keskar's keynote focused on Microsoft's evolving strategy to empower healthcare research through responsible and data-centric generative AI (GenAI). His keynote addressed a central question faced by researchers, especially in the healthcare domain: how to advance their AI-driven innovative research without being overwhelmed by technical infrastructure, data complexity and compliance.

The central focus of Harshad's talk was the complexity and sensitivity of healthcare datasets that underpin AI applications in clinical and research settings. He emphasised that the vast majority of healthcare data is unstructured and multimodal, encompassing medical imaging, clinical notes, biosignals, and genomics. These datasets are often fragmented across departments, hospitals, and research institutions, making them difficult to access, integrate, or curate for AI model training.

To address this, Harshad described Microsoft's end-to-end healthcare AI stack, grounded in:

- **Medical foundation models:** Out-of-the-box large language models (LLMs) that handle multimodal data like GPT-4o¹³, are not equipped to handle this kind of input. In response, Microsoft is investing in specialised foundation models designed for pathology, radiology, and other modalities through the Azure AI Studio model catalogue¹⁴.
- **Azure Trusted Research Environments (TREs):** Secure, auditable, and privacy-preserving infrastructures, co-developed with institutions including **The Alan Turing**

¹³ <https://openai.com/index/hello-gpt-4o/>

¹⁴ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/ai-foundry/how-to/healthcare-ai/healthcare-ai-models>

Institute (Safe Data Haven TRE¹⁵). These platforms enable sensitive data to be processed, analysed, and modelled with embedded compliance and role-based access.

- **Data harmonisation at scale:** Leveraging standards like Health Level Seven International (HL7) FHIR¹⁶, Microsoft’s pipeline tools automate the conversion of legacy healthcare data formats into AI-ready form.

Harshad also highlighted impactful use cases based on the Microsoft healthcare AI stack including:

Cancer imaging solutions, co-developed with NHS partners¹⁷, uses automated diagnostics on mammograms and pathology slides

Project X-Vivo¹⁸, a genomics-driven initiative with the Broad Institute, identifies cancer biomarkers using Azure TREs and multimodal LLMs;

Keskar argued that embedding governance into infrastructure ensures AI systems are not just performant but are also robust and compliant.

While Harshad emphasised the immense potential of AI in healthcare, he concluded with a key insight:

“If your AI strategy doesn’t include your data strategy, it’s incomplete. You can’t build health AI on shaky data or infrastructure.”- Harshad Keskar

Audience Q&A with Harshad Keskar: Highlights

The participants had many questions on responsible AI in healthcare settings, governance, data management, and standards. Below are the highlights of their exchange with Harshad:

- **On the 99% statistic claim regarding unstructured healthcare data:** Harshad clarified that this statistic refers to the data volume particularly from high-resolution imaging, and biosignals.
- **On promoting open standards and model interoperability:** He noted that Microsoft actively contributes to global data interoperability efforts,

¹⁵ https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/v1.0.0/evaluations/alan_turing_institute.html

¹⁶ <https://hl7.org/fhir/>

¹⁷ <https://ukstories.microsoft.com/features/12-more-breast-cancers-detected-with-potential-workload-savings-of-30-in-the-uks-first-prospective-evaluation-of-breast-screening-ai/>

¹⁸ <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/project-ex-vivo/>

including HL7 FHIR and SNOMED CT¹⁹, and develops tools with embedded ontologies. Copilots and RAG-based services are designed to work across platforms via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs).

- **On responsible and explainable AI in health and clinical settings:** Harshad explained that model transparency is ensured through embedded prompts, documentation of intended use, and support for clinician-in-the-loop workflows. Azure-hosted models must be fine-tuned and deployed under institutional oversight, ensuring safety and local context alignment.
- **On accountability and model governance:** He emphasised that institutions maintain control of their custom workflows, and Azure ensures tenant isolation, meaning researchers' data isn't reused by Microsoft for pretraining.

3.3 Advancing AI-Readiness at Research Data Repositories: Reyna Jenkyns

Speaker: Reyna Jenkyns, Associate Director, World Data System International Technology Office, Victoria, Canada, 2025, May 13

Reyna Jenkyns' keynote explored the evolving role of data repositories in enabling responsible, bias-aware AI systems. Representing the World Data System (WDS) and its collaboration with Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP), she presented a pilot initiative that assesses and strengthens AI readiness in scientific data repositories.

Her keynote speech revolved around the ESIP AI Readiness Checklist developed to evaluate whether datasets are suitable for machine learning and AI applications.

The checklist evaluates factors such as metadata quality, documentation, data preparation and access as shown in Figure 3.

¹⁹ <https://www.snomed.org/use-snomed-ct>

ESIP AI Data Readiness Checklist

ESIP Data Readiness Cluster (2023). Checklist to Examine AI-readiness for Open Environmental Datasets. Version 1.0. Earth Science Information Partners. <https://github.com/ESIPFed/data-readiness> [2023-11].

Figure 3: ESIP Data Readiness checklist

Reyna also presented the early results on the application of the checklist stemming from the WDS workshop on AI Readiness in October 2024, and follow-on pilot. They include:

- A 12-repository pilot cohort across multiple disciplines revealed common readiness gaps in metadata completeness, documentation clarity, and bias declarations, especially around dynamic or sensitive datasets.
- Participant feedback requests included enhanced checklist support, including clearer terminology, scoring guidance, and fields to capture ethical context such as CARE²⁰ principles and prior AI model usage.
- Refinements under way include a revised checklist, automation prototypes using the F-UJI FAIR checker²¹, and alignment with infrastructures like digital twins, data spaces, and Trusted Research Environments (TREs).
- The effort is linked to broader policy-level work through participation in the UN Data Governance Working Group²² and the FORCE11 Typologies initiative²³, focused on interoperable metadata that links datasets to AI model training and deployment.

²⁰ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>

²¹ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

²² <https://unctad.org/meeting/first-meeting-un-cstd-multi-stakeholder-working-group-data-governance-all-levels>

²³ <https://force11.org/group/data-usage-typologies/>

“We really needed to advance the data repository readiness... for AI. Repositories should curate data not just for access, but to make it machine-actionable, so that it’s AI ready” - Reyna Jenkyns

Audience Q&A with Reyna Jenkyns: Highlights

The key areas of audience engagement focused on transferability of the ESIP checklist to other research domains and the overlap with existing frameworks.

- On **healthcare applicability**, Jenkyns confirmed the checklist worked with minimal modification in a health repository, and efforts to refine it to the health data space are ongoing.
- **On aligning with standards**, related to MLCommons/Croissant²⁴, Reyna emphasised that the mode of thinking of ESIP checklist going forward is that of harmonisation, not duplication.
- **On the next steps**, she encouraged repositories to join upcoming cohorts and help embed AI-readiness into certification and infrastructure governance frameworks.

3.4 Accelerating Research Workflows with Data-Centric Small Language Models

Speaker: Haritha Thilakarathne, Cloud Solution Architect (AI), Microsoft, Sydney, Australia, 2025, 15 May

Haritha Thilakarathne’s keynote explored the evolving role of Small Language Models (SLMs) in advancing research workflows through a data-centric AI lens. While large-scale LLMs have dominated AI discourse, he emphasised that the next phase of scientific impact will come from smaller, domain-specific models that integrate more naturally with institutional research ecosystems. Unlike general purpose models, SLMs require less compute, allowing for faster iteration, and better support tool integration, reproducibility, and domain context. Haritha presented Microsoft’s Open Phi model family (shown in Figure 4) and Azure AI Foundry as key enablers of this approach. These platforms support agentic orchestration, allowing multiple SLMs to collaborate across scientific tasks. Central to his argument was the shift from a model-centric to a data-centric paradigm. Explaining this paradigm shift, Haritha stressed that model performance depends more on dataset quality than model complexity.

²⁴ <https://mlcommons.org/working-groups/data/croissant/>

Figure 4: Open model family of Microsoft’s Phi

Haritha also showcased real-world applications such as BioBERT²⁵ for biomedical literature mining, where Microsoft worked with biomedical partners to fine-tune BioBERT, demonstrating that small models can deliver high-impact results when trained on well-curated, domain-specific datasets.

Key insights from Haritha’s talk include:

- Gartner predicts that by 2027, SLMs will be used at least 3x more than LLMs, driven by their efficiency, adaptability, and integration potential²⁶.
- SLMs like the Microsoft Phi family support modular workflows that are domain-tuned, cost-effective, and easier to govern than massive, centralised models especially when sensitive data are involved.
- The shift to data-centric AI prioritises dataset curation, documentation, and bias-awareness over sheer model size and compute power.

²⁵ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/36/4/1234/5566506>

²⁶ <https://www.gartner.com/en/newsroom/press-releases/2025-04-09-gartner-predicts-by-2027-organizations-will-use-small-task-specific-ai-models-three-times-more-than-general-purpose-large-language-models>

He concluded by calling for better metadata, dataset governance, and equitable access to lightweight AI infrastructure.

“We always say garbage in, garbage out, and that hasn’t changed! Even with the smartest (AI) models, the quality of your data really matters.” - Haritha Thilakarathne

Audience Q&A with Haritha Thilakarathne: Highlights

Haritha Thilakarathne’s session sparked some of the most engaging dialogue of the roundtable, with participants discussing pressing topics of bias, underrepresentation of data, limits of scaling, and the relation to non-LLM AI models.

- **On the limits of model scaling**, Haritha agreed with audience concerns that increasing layers no longer guarantees improved performance. He acknowledged the growing view that AI scaling laws are plateauing and reinforced the shift toward smaller, efficient models with good quality data.
- **On Mixture of Experts (MoE) architectures**, he responded to questions about architectural evolution by noting that third-generation LLMs are already leveraging MoE designs, essentially mimicking the modular behaviour of SLMs.
- **On multilingual bias**, Haritha acknowledged that over 90% of existing LLM training data is English-dominated. He emphasized that inclusive AI requires region-specific fine-tuning and better multilingual evaluation to avoid digital exclusion.
- **On edge deployment**, he explained that Microsoft is embedding SLMs in Copilot+ PCs and IoT devices to enable privacy-preserving, real-time AI inference without relying solely on the cloud.

3.5 AI-Driven Innovation Strategies for Data Curation and Management in International Collaborative Research: Mukkesh Kumar

Speaker: Mukkesh Kumar, Head of Data Management Platform, A*STAR, Singapore, 2025, 15 May

Dr. Mukkesh Kumar’s presentation addressed Singapore’s national strategy to advance AI-enabled research through standardised data curation, secure infrastructures, and cross-border collaboration. The OMOP data curation efforts with MOH TRUST are advancing into community-based practices in Singapore, establishing the national data

standards for research. MOH TRUST²⁷ and the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) serve as pillars of Singapore’s data readiness for AI.

He presented a case study from Singapore’s Surgical Risk Prediction Project, where curated data was converted into OMOP-CDM²⁸ format and integrated with Azure’s AI infrastructure to train and validate AI models under real-world conditions. The talk underscored that data harmonisation and trust infrastructures (like Trusted Research Environments (TREs)) are key enablers for reproducible, scalable, and ethically grounded AI.

Key elements included:

- Use of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) like MOH TRUST to ensure secure, compliant access to linked clinical-genomic data
- Adoption of OMOP-CDM to standardise healthcare data and participate in the global OHDSI²⁹ research network
- Development of agentic AI tools integrated with curated datasets for patient risk profiling, powered by GPT-4o and Azure AI Foundry³⁰

“We don’t curate just for access, we curate to ensure data trust and AI-readiness at scale.” - Mukkesh Kumar

Audience Q&A with Mukkesh Kumar: Highlights

- On the role of OMOP-CDM: Kumar explained its importance in enabling data interoperability and comparative effectiveness in research across jurisdictions. Harmonisation helps lower the barrier to participating in international studies without compromising local governance.
- On TRE architecture: He clarified that MOH TRUST integrates ethical review, identity masking, audit logs, and fine-grained access policies, making it a production-grade infrastructure for collaborative AI development.
- On deploying agentic AI: A question on AI use in clinical workflows led to the example of a chatbot-like assistant trained to simulate surgical risk assessments using

²⁷ <https://trustplatform.sg/>

²⁸ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

²⁹ <https://www.ohdsi.org/data-standardization/>

³⁰ <https://ai.azure.com/>

structured patient data. “These AI agents are decision-support, not decision-makers,” he emphasized.

- On reproducibility: He stressed that model generalisability depends heavily on curated, standardised, and de-biased data, not just advanced algorithms.

3.6 Generative AI and AI for Science: Kyong-Ha Lee

Speaker: Kyong-ha Lee, Head, Large-scale AI Research Center, KISTI & Professor at UST, Korea

Dr. Kyong-Ha Lee delivered a compelling keynote exploring how the role of AI in scientific discovery is shifting from analytical support to autonomous innovation. He positioned this transition within the broader concept of the "Fifth Paradigm of Science" as shown in Figure 5, where Generative AI agents are not only assisting but also driving scientific inquiry, hypothesis generation, and experiment design.

Figure 5: The evolution of research paradigms, Slide from Kyong-ha Lee’s talk

He introduced KISTI’s KONI (Knowledge-Oriented Neural Intelligence) ³¹ as an exemplar of this shift. KONI is designed to integrate multimodal data—from research papers,

³¹

https://www.kisti.re.kr/eng/news/post/eng_news/6610;jsessionid=VnkGjW8s1NFFnroCOEqWogZTRtCk vPv7VIHk2oqZdKWe3sTvnme3BRDaAzgBtaN.ar211_servlet_engine23?t=1742860800054

databases, and lab sensors, and work with Large Action Models (LAMs)³² and LLMs to perform complex tasks autonomously. These agents help plan scientific experiments, run simulations, and communicate findings in a human-readable format.

Key highlights of the talk include:

- Scientific AI agents are being developed to act beyond co-pilots, functioning as collaborative planners capable of executing iterative research tasks and self-evaluating results.
- The KONI platform, part of Korea’s national investment in AI for science, is currently used in nuclear fusion, climate modelling, and materials design.
- Dr. Lee emphasised the convergence of Language Models (LLMs) and Large Action Models (LAMs)³³, which allow AI systems to move beyond text processing and engage directly with experimental environments and high-performance computing systems.
- A defining challenge is the legal uncertainty surrounding AI-generated content and training data. As LLMs increasingly contribute to writing, coding, and modelling, the ownership and attribution of AI-generated knowledge remain unresolved.
- He highlighted the urgent need for international ethical standards, arguing that AI must be guided by a scientific social contract, just like human researchers.

This framing underscored a core tension: while AI is accelerating discovery, it also prompts deep questions about authorship, reproducibility, and the epistemology of machine-generated science. Dr. Lee called for international collaboration to build robust governance frameworks that ensure AI-augmented science remains open, reproducible, and aligned with human values.

“We are not just using AI to assist science, we are training AI to conduct science. The future of science will be shaped by teams of human and AI researchers working in tandem. This partnership must be grounded in trust, explainability, and shared purpose.” - Kyong-Ha Lee

Audience Q&A with Kyong-Ha Lee: Highlights

- **On the role of the researcher in an AI-enabled future:** One participant posed a pointed question- *“What is the role of the researcher if AI is doing the research?”* Dr. Lee responded by emphasising that researchers will not be replaced but rather **augmented** by AI. He likened AI to a "co-pilot" in the research process: automating

³² <https://www.datacamp.com/blog/large-action-models>

³³ <https://www.datacamp.com/blog/large-action-models>

routine or data-intensive tasks so that humans can focus on framing the right questions, ethical implications, and creative exploration. “AI should empower curiosity,” he remarked, “not replace it.”

- **On ethical implications of AI-generated science:** Dr. Lee noted the need for new ethical frameworks to evaluate the provenance, attribution, and reproducibility of AI-generated hypotheses and insights. He emphasised that without human oversight, there is a risk of “hallucinated science”, outputs that seem valid but lack grounding.
- **On infrastructural readiness:** Responding to a question about deploying such systems in real laboratories, he outlined that KISTI’s KONI platform is already being trialled in simulations for nuclear fusion experiments, integrating multimodal data, scientific literature, and lab instrumentation to support AI-driven workflows.
- **On international cooperation:** He reiterated the importance of **cross-border frameworks** for both AI development and governance in science, calling for a “multilateral charter” akin to Open Science declarations.

To deepen the dialogue beyond the keynotes, participants engaged in moderated breakout sessions focussed on core themes of data and AI. The following section provides insights from these discussions.

4. Key Insights from Breakout Interactions

To encourage focused and meaningful discussions, participants were divided into small breakout groups to explore three key thematic topics: **Data Readiness for AI**, **AI in Research**, and **AI Governance**. Each participant engaged in discussions on all three topics to gain a well-rounded understanding.

Every breakout room was facilitated by a moderator and followed the **Rose, Thorn, Bud**³⁴ approach. This method encouraged participants to identify positive aspects (Rose), challenges (Thorn), and opportunities (Bud) for each topic in a series of short, structured intervals. Insights from these discussions were recorded anonymously using an online interactive tool called [Excalidraw](#). At the end of the breakout sessions, moderators returned to the plenary (main room) to present the most significant Rose, Thorn, and Bud for each topic, based on the group discussions.

In the following paragraph we highlight the key insights on the three main topics of **Data Readiness for AI**, **AI in Research** and **AI Governance across** both the roundtables. The

³⁴ <https://www.colorado.edu/researchinnovation/rose-bud-thorn>

discussion overviews from the individual breakout rooms on 13 May and 15 May sessions are listed in [Appendix C](#).

Data Readiness for AI

Participants across both roundtables reflected growing awareness of what it means to be **AI-ready**, encompassing **FAIR principles**, data quality, transparency, openness, and ethical considerations.

The importance of **trustworthy, bias-aware, and complete datasets** was strongly emphasised, particularly in fields where model outputs have real-world implications. Participants identified tools such as **standardised APIs**, metadata formats, and readiness checklists as practical aids in improving AI readiness. Progress was also reported in the **uniform description of datasets** and **adoption of metadata standards**.

However, **implementation challenges** persist. Key barriers include a **shortage of skilled personnel**, the need for **targeted training**, and **infrastructure and cost constraints**, especially for data cleaning and quality control. Even well-documented datasets often suffer from persistent issues related to **bias, provenance, and reproducibility**. Many datasets remain **context-bound** and not readily fit for AI use, with **contextual misalignment** frequently cited.

Participants stressed the need for more **inclusive, multilingual, and geographically representative datasets**, alongside greater **transparency** to mitigate the risks of AI functioning as a “**black box**”.

Improvements in **data processing platforms** are beginning to ease some burdens, and growing attention to **data quality assessment tools** reflects increasing scrutiny of AI training inputs. Looking ahead, participants saw strong potential in **emerging tools and frameworks** to embed AI readiness not just technically, but institutionally. AI itself can support this effort through **automated schema generation, metadata enrichment, and interoperability solutions**. Virtual research environments, such as **digital twins**, were cited as effective for enabling **repeatable, governed data workflows**. There was shared agreement that investing in **domain-specific standards, curated small models, and FAIR implementation profiles for AI** is critical to ensuring systemic readiness and responsible adoption.

AI in Research

Participants expressed strong optimism about the **transformative potential of AI** in scientific research. Across disciplines such as **cell biology, climate science, healthcare** and **biomedical modelling**, AI is enabling researchers to work with increasingly complex, **multimodal datasets**, draw new inferences, and accelerate

discovery. It is also facilitating breakthroughs including **protein structure modelling** and **in-silico experimentation**, reducing reliance on traditional laboratory trials.

AI was widely regarded as a powerful tool for **summarising, analysing** and **managing large volumes of data**, particularly within the **life sciences**. The use of **Large Language Models (LLMs)** was noted for reducing time and costs in research workflows, allowing scientists to focus on **hypothesis-driven work**. Participants also described the value of **domain-specific machine learning models** embedded in accessible interfaces, such as **chatbots**, which support **modular** and **researcher-friendly workflows**.

The pace of **AI innovation** was seen as both an opportunity and a challenge. On one hand, it enables quicker adoption and experimentation. On the other, it contributes to pressure and uncertainty, especially in institutions lacking **infrastructure** or formal support. Participants emphasised the importance of **AI literacy, critical thinking**, and **targeted training** to ensure responsible and informed engagement with tools. **Small language models (SLMs)** were welcomed for their accessibility and adaptability, though it was noted that these too require careful scrutiny, particularly in settings affected by **limited computing capacity** or the **digital divide**.

Despite the enthusiasm, **reproducibility** and **research integrity** were recurring concerns. Participants consistently reported that the **quality** and **documentation** of datasets and models were variable, undermining reliability and limiting reuse. There was also concern that **pressure to publish** may discourage transparency around **methods** and **model design**. There was also a clear lack of institutional and journal guidelines on AI usage in research.

To address these issues, several emerging practices were highlighted. The **Model Openness Framework** was cited as a helpful structure for improving **model sharing, documentation** and **reporting**. Wider adoption of **reproducibility-first protocols, AI-specific metadata standards**, and **interdisciplinary data sharing** were all identified as high-potential strategies to strengthen **accountability** and **collaboration**.

AI Governance

Governance was recognised as a **critical yet lagging component** of the AI ecosystem. Participants welcomed the emergence of new **regulatory frameworks** from global institutions such as **UNESCO's AI recommendations**, the **EU AI Act**, and national policy roadmaps, which were viewed as signs of positive momentum. Many research-performing organisations are beginning to embed local policies and institutional

guidelines, while international bodies such as **Creative Commons** are starting to address issues such as **open licensing** in the AI context.

At the same time, participants expressed concern that **regulatory development is not keeping pace with technological innovation**. The challenge of balancing **innovation with ethics and compliance** was a recurring theme. This tension, often framed as the “**trust versus speed**” dilemma, reflected concerns that institutions must act swiftly to harness AI’s benefits, yet cannot afford to ignore crucial safeguards around **safety, reproducibility, and bias**. The difficulty of managing **privacy versus data sharing** was also emphasised, especially where sensitive datasets are essential for training models but difficult to use ethically and legally.

Despite these challenges, participants saw hope in **community-led and cross-institutional approaches**. Suggestions included the use of **scenario planning tools** to help policy-makers and researchers prepare for multiple AI futures, and the development of **best practice repositories** and **university-level AI policies** to institutionalise governance processes. Geographical differences in AI governance approaches were also discussed, with the **European Union** identified as a leader in regulatory development.

There was strong interest in the growing role of **international standards**, particularly **ISO 42001**, and the contributions of organisations such as the **Research Data Alliance (RDA)** in promoting **globally harmonised governance frameworks**. Participants stressed that **AI should serve people, not the other way around**, and highlighted the broader **socioeconomic implications of automation**, including **job displacement** and the need for **re-skilling**.

Concerns were raised about **non-evidence-based policymaking**, especially in contexts where AI investment or legislation is influenced more by hype than substance. A lack of **governance literacy**, not only among researchers but also among policymakers, was seen as a significant barrier. Promoting **transparency** and **public trust** in how AI is explained, deployed and regulated was identified as a key opportunity for future work.

While the **fragmentation of governance across geographies** was seen as a barrier, there was also recognition of positive developments. The emergence of **shared standards** and increased awareness of AI’s **societal impacts** are gradually creating the conditions for more **responsible deployment**. Participants highlighted the importance of practical tools and infrastructure, such as **MLOps practices, auditable pipelines, and role-based access controls**, in supporting scalable and effective AI governance.

The breakout discussions revealed a wide range of **practical insights**, **shared challenges**, and **emerging opportunities** voiced by a globally diverse research community. Building on these reflections, the next section presents the key findings and corresponding recommendations that emerged from the roundtable sessions on **Data and AI**.

5. Findings and Recommendations

Both global sessions provided rich and diverse insights into the evolving intersection of data, artificial intelligence, and research practice. Drawing on discussions from keynote speeches, audience interactions in chat and in speech, breakout room exchanges, and real-time polling, we applied a thematic analysis approach to identify the eight key findings presented in this paper. The findings were consistent across both global sessions, with no major divergence in participant perspectives. In several instances, the discussions were further reinforced or influenced by keynote presentations. To aid navigation, the recommendations are listed at the outset and elaborated in the pages that follow.

- Top skilling needs are prompting, agentic AI, and data for AI – with ethics and critical thinking
- AI use in research: writing, coding assistance, productivity are dominant use cases – gaps in usage guidance remain
- Researchers must be empowered by AI, not replaced, but concerns run deep
- AI is progressing on shaky data foundations: data readiness is imperative
- Small models and good data for AI efficiency and democratisation
- Secure and scalable environments emerge as essential infrastructure for trust
- Responsible AI in research: reproducibility and data ethics key challenges to overcome
- Agreement on AI regulation is unanimous but implementation fragmented and playing catch-up

5.1 Top Skilling Needs: Prompting, Agentic AI, and Data for AI – with Ethics and Critical Thinking

Participants across both global sessions identified a wide spectrum of skills necessary to keep pace with rapidly advancing AI technologies. While specific priorities varied,

there was strong consensus around a few recurring themes. **Prompt engineering**³⁵ and **Agentic AI**³⁶ emerged as top areas of interest, as illustrated in Figure 6, closely followed by **data science skills** including **data engineering, preparation, and data processing for AI applications**— the key elements of Data Readiness.

Importantly, beyond the live polling, participants placed consistent emphasis on **skills related to responsible AI**, with recurring discussions on **bias detection and mitigation, privacy, security**, and the handling of **sensitive data**, particularly in domains like healthcare, environmental science, and social research. These issues were discussed not only in breakout groups but also highlighted in the keynote sessions and participant Q&As, indicating their broad relevance across disciplinary and regional contexts.

³⁵ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/shows/generative-ai-for-beginners/understanding-prompt-engineering-fundamentals-generative-ai-for-beginners>

³⁶ <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/what-is-agentic-ai/>

Data and AI skills needed to advance research capabilities

Americas, Europe and Africa session

Asia and Oceania session

Figure 6: Audience responses on the skills they would like to learn to enhance their research

Beyond technical competencies, the sessions revealed a strong call for embedding **critical thinking, judgement, and ethical reflexivity** into individual and institutional AI skilling strategies.

Participants pointed out that while AI tools offer unprecedented opportunities, they also demand a thoughtful understanding of risk, fairness, and accountability. As one rapporteur noted, ethical rigour must become a foundational part of scientific literacy, not a bolt-on.

The emphasis on **Technical AI literacy, ethical reasoning, and privacy-aware deployment** underscores the need for a more holistic approach to skills development, leading us to provide the following recommendation:

RECOMMENDATION: EVOLVING WITH THE FIELD – BLENDING INDIVIDUAL INITIATIVE AND INSTITUTIONAL STRATEGY

Given the pace at which the AI field is evolving, it is essential that skills development efforts remain current, adaptable, and multidimensional. For individuals, there are numerous publicly (freely) available resources offering up-to-date training in technical AI skills. These include initiatives from both public and private partners such as [Google’s Learn AI Skills](#) and [Microsoft Learn for AI](#), which often provide free, flexible, high-quality learning paths for developers, researchers and domain experts of all expertise levels.

At the institutional level, efforts should go beyond traditional technical training to include interdisciplinary and ethically grounded approaches. Models such as the National Science Foundation’s NRT (National Research Trainee) programme on Ethical AI Research in the United States³⁷ offer a valuable blueprint. These initiatives combine technical rigour with education in ethics, policy, and human-centred design, preparing researchers to both develop and critically evaluate AI systems.

5.2 AI Use in Research: Writing, Coding Assistance, Productivity-Gaps in Usage Guidance Remain

The roundtables revealed a strong convergence in how AI is being used: for many researchers, AI’s most immediate value lies in productivity gains and shown in Figure 7. Across disciplines and regions, participants shared how they were already using

³⁷ <https://www.nsf.gov/funding/initiatives/nrt/advancing-ethical-ai-through-convergent-research>

generative AI to streamline academic writing, assist with code development, summarise literature and content, and for generating content like emails and templates.

AI use cases

Americas, Europe and Africa session

Asia and Oceania session

Figure 7: An illustration of the most common research use cases of AI

In both plenaries and breakout rooms, early-career and senior researchers alike described integrating tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot, and Claude into their research workflows. “I use it to help with structuring my papers,” one participant shared, while another noted its utility in writing grant proposals and generating ideas for code debugging. Poll results from both Menti sessions corroborated this trend, with **writing assistance** and **coding support** ranking among the top AI use cases across all regions.

Importantly, the discussions also highlighted sharp disparities in access to these tools. While some institutions had rolled out enterprise-level AI platforms or supported faculty training, others left researchers to navigate AI experimentation independently.

Importantly, participants described a notable **lack of institutional guidance and publisher policies** on what constitutes responsible use, how to acknowledge AI assistance in publications, and how to ensure **transparency and reproducibility** when AI tools are embedded in research processes.

This variation in individual use is reflected in institutional approaches to AI.

Figure 8: AI Readiness levels of participants’ institutions

As shown in Figure 8, participants reported a clear divide: some institutions are still in the early stages of adoption, with exploratory or ad hoc use of AI tools, while others have moved towards more advanced integration. The latter group is significantly more likely to

have formal guidance, internal policies, and a defined AI strategy or institutional vision to support responsible deployment.

RECOMMENDATION: INSTITUTIONS AND PUBLISHERS SHOULD OFFER USAGE AND DISCLOSURE GUIDANCE

These insights were also reflected in a February 2025 *Nature* survey³⁸, which found widespread use of generative AI by researchers but little institutional guidance on usage and disclosure.

Based on these findings, the key recommendations on AI use in research include:

- Both institutions and publishers should provide clear, context-sensitive guidance to responsibly **disclose AI use in writing, coding, and analysis**.
- Institutions should establish vetted access to secure, research-appropriate AI platforms that meet data protection and security standards and respect institutional policies
- While the guidance of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE)³⁹ and *Nature*⁴⁰ are examples of preliminary efforts, norms remain in flux, presenting a timely opportunity for research communities such as the RDA to play a leading role in shaping field-appropriate guidance.

5.3 Researchers Must Be Empowered by AI, Not Replaced — But Concerns Run Deep

Although the prevailing tone across the roundtables framed AI as a catalyst for enhancing research, an underlying unease ran through many discussions. Participants acknowledged AI’s potential to broaden **access to knowledge, accelerate analysis, and support new forms of inquiry**. Yet this optimism was tempered by the fear that such advances could come at the cost of labour security, equity, and academic agency.

One academic questioned, **“If writing, coding, and analysis can all be automated, then why would institutions keep junior researchers at all?”**. Many early-career scholars already face insecure contracts, limited supervision, and performance frameworks driven by publication metrics.

³⁸ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-025-00343-5>

³⁹ <https://publicationethics.org/topic-discussions/guidance-use-artificial-intelligence>

⁴⁰ <https://www.nature.com/nature-portfolio/editorial-policies/ai>

Others highlighted the pressure to rapidly acquire AI literacy in a fast-evolving field, particularly in environments with limited institutional infrastructure or uneven access to training.

Participants warned that, without safeguards, AI risks entrenching global inequalities by privileging data-rich, English-speaking environments, while excluding researchers without access to computing power, infrastructure, or well-curated training data. These concerns align with broader concerns related to the deskilling of research roles (“cognitive laziness”), the decline of mentoring pathways, and the erosion of interpretive agency in automated knowledge production.

Still, the mood was not one of resistance but of cautious and thoughtful enhancement with AI, a participant summed up: “The fear is not the technology, it’s the decisions made using it.”

RECOMMENDATION: CENTRE HUMAN AGENCY AND SKILLING IN AI-INTEGRATED RESEARCH

To realise the promise of AI powered research responsibly, institutions must treat AI skilling not just as a technical requirement, but as a foundation for **epistemic agency**, the ability of researchers to understand, question, evaluate, and guide AI use in their own domains.

Crucially, AI skilling must also be framed as a matter of academic sovereignty. Researchers need support not only to operate AI tools, but to evaluate their appropriateness for specific research questions, reject systems that compromise scientific integrity, and contribute to the development of AI methods aligned with the values of their discipline. This includes training in model interpretability, algorithmic bias detection, and data governance, as well as structured opportunities to provide feedback on institutional AI procurement and deployment.

To that end, institutions should:

- Integrate AI literacy into doctoral and early-career development programmes
- Ensure researchers have continuous access to high-quality, domain-specific training in a rapidly changing field
- Support peer-led and interdisciplinary learning environments that foster reflection, critique and co-design of AI use in research practice

These actions also reflect the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI, which calls for inclusive AI education that advances both technical skill and human autonomy⁴¹ while advancing science with the power of AI⁴².

5.4 AI is Progressing on Shaky Data Foundations: Data Readiness is Imperative

“We don’t need more data (for AI), we need better data.”

Across both global sessions, participants voiced deep concern that while AI systems are evolving rapidly, the foundational layer of data remains uneven, fragmented, and often unfit for purpose.

Across both sessions, participants highlighted recurring issues such as **missing metadata, poor documentation**, incompatible formats, and **unclear licensing**, all of which hinder data readiness for AI and reproducibility. In particular, those working in environmental science, health, and social research pointed to the challenges of navigating sensitive, siloed, or non-standardised datasets. In many institutions, participants reported that data preparation for AI applications still relies on manual effort. Responsibility for data documentation often defaults to individuals, with no shared templates or tooling. Several groups noted the absence of automated pipelines and the high cost of retrofitting legacy datasets, especially in cross-domain or longitudinal research.

The keynote discussions reinforced these gaps. Requirements for “representative, complete, and statistically appropriate” datasets are rarely operationalised. In regulated domains, participants stressed that readiness failures directly block responsible AI deployment.

RECOMMENDATION: CLOSING THE DATA READINESS FOR AI GAP

- Researchers as well as data repositories should follow evaluation frameworks such as the ESIP AI Readiness Checklist, FAIR implementation profiles, and datasheets.
- Institutions and research groups should invest in automation tools for schema inference, metadata enrichment, and quality control, aligned with FAIR principles and emerging standards such as HL7 FHIR

⁴¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000381137>

⁴² <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000381137>

- Institutions should encourage data stewardship roles within research teams to maintain documentation, manage provenance, and coordinate compliance across workflows
- Funders should link data readiness to funding and review processes by requiring readiness planning as part of grant submissions involving AI related projects.

5.5 Small Models and Good Data for AI Efficiency and Democratisation

Participants across sessions identified a strong shift toward small language models (SLMs) as a responsible and adaptable alternative to general-purpose LLMs. This shift was framed not only in terms of technical performance, but also **access, cost, sustainability, and research equity**.

Speakers and participants emphasised that SLMs are easier to train, require less compute, and are deployable in diverse environments, including cloud, local machines, and mobile devices.

Smallest AI models scoring above 60% on MMLU, 2022–24
Source: Abdin et al., 2024 | Chart: 2025 AI Index report

Figure 9: Stanford AI Index Report⁴³ shows the reducing size of high performing AI models

Environmental and infrastructure concerns featured prominently in the discussion. Large models were described as energy-intensive and exclusionary, particularly for institutions with limited computational capacity. Participants noted that SLMs can be

⁴³ <https://hai.stanford.edu/ai-index/2025-ai-index-report>

deployed flexibly on-device via tools like LM Studio or in the cloud, offering adaptable solutions across research environments.

Most SLMs are also **openly available**, which supports broader research participation. Discussions highlighted that when paired with **highly curated, domain-specific data**, SLMs deliver consistently strong results. Research from Stanford was cited showing that **small models are now performing competitively on the (Measuring Massive Multitask Language Understanding) MMLU benchmark**, as shown in Figure 9, reinforcing the view that scale is no longer the sole determinant of capability. Participants saw this as an encouraging shift toward **responsible, data-centric AI**.

RECOMMENDATION: LEAD THE PARADIGM SHIFT FROM MODEL-CENTRIC TO DATA-CENTRIC AI

Institutions and funders should:

- Prioritise development and deployment of small, domain-specific models as default infrastructure for research use cases, particularly in sensitive or resource-constrained settings
- Invest in the curation of high-quality, domain-specific datasets to support reproducible and task-relevant model performance
- Treat open and small model accessibility as a driver of research democratisation, enabling participation by researchers in the global South
- Encourage research and funding focused on the small model paradigm and high-quality data practices

5.6 Secure and Scalable Environments emerge as Essential Infrastructure for Trust

Participants across both sessions consistently pointed to **Trusted Research Environments (TREs)**, **regulatory sandboxes**, and **federated platforms** as essential infrastructure for responsible AI in research. These environments were described not only as technical solutions but as **operational indicators of trust, readiness, and governance maturity**.

Multiple breakout groups cited TREs as enablers of secure collaboration and privacy-preserving research. Rather than treating data access, governance, and AI development as separate workflows, these platforms integrate them. Several participants described

TREs as “*compliance built into infrastructure*”, supporting sensitive research in fields such as healthcare, genomics, and social science.

The effectiveness of **regulatory sandboxes** also featured prominently in a plenary discussion, Keynotes reinforced these views with further real-world examples include:

- Azure Trusted Research Environments used in clinical genomics projects to manage role-based access and audit logs
- Singapore’s MOH TRUST platform, which combines ethical review, identity masking, and structured consent for cross-border clinical AI training

Breakout groups emphasised that secure environments reduce barriers to collaboration, support reproducibility, and accelerate governance adoption. Participants called for **automated risk management workflows**, and **modular secure platforms** that allow research institutions to embed responsible AI at scale.

RECOMMENDATION: PRIORITISE PRIVACY-PRESERVING, SECURE TESTING ENVIRONMENTS

Institutions and funders should:

- Provision access to production-grade Trusted Research Environments (TREs) that support privacy-preserving AI workflows, with support for secure multi-party computation, pseudonymisation, audit logging, and reproducible modelling pipelines
- Treat TREs and regulatory sandboxes as infrastructure for compliance automation, embedding frameworks aligned with data protection law (e.g. GDPR), medical data standards (e.g. HL7-FHIR), and model cards
- Enable federated, schema-aligned deployments across institutional boundaries using shared ontologies and data harmonisation framework

5.7 Responsible AI in Research: Reproducibility and Data Ethics Key Challenges to Overcome

Responsible Artificial Intelligence (Responsible AI) is an umbrella terms for approach to developing, assessing, and deploying AI systems in a safe, trustworthy, and ethical way.

Despite strong agreement on the need for ethical AI, participants across all sessions acknowledged that responsible AI practice remains uneven, particularly in areas related to **bias detection, data ownership, Indigenous rights, and copyright attribution**.

Bias was described not as an anomaly but a **systemic feature of training data**, often inherited from non-representative data sources, geographic gaps, or language imbalances. Across both sessions, participants highlighted the lack of shared standards for declaring or mitigating bias. Several noted that current datasets are optimised for performance benchmarks but fail to include fields for representativeness or limitations.

Copyright and authorship surfaced as emerging points of friction. As AI-generated content becomes more prevalent, researchers reported confusion over ownership, attribution, and reuse.

Reproducibility was cited as the most actionable and cross-cutting entry point for responsible AI. Participants described widespread issues such as missing documentation, version control, and opaque preprocessing pipelines. These limitations prevent peer review, replication, and verification, undermining the scientific method and rigour. As one participant put it, “*You can’t call it responsible if no one can reproduce it, trace it, or tell where it came from.*” Without decisive reforms, the reproducibility crisis already facing science risks being amplified by AI.

RECOMMENDATION: OPERATIONALISE RESPONSIBLE AI THROUGH REPRODUCIBILITY, RIGHTS, AND REPRESENTATIVENESS

To advance responsible AI from aspiration to implementation, research institutions, funders, technology and infrastructure providers should:

- Adopt reproducibility protocols using structured tools such as *Datasheets for Datasets*, *Model Cards*, and the *Model Openness Framework (MOF)*, ensuring version tracking, documentation, and transparent preprocessing pipelines
- Require bias declarations and require fields for dataset representativeness, known exclusions, and demographic coverage as part of AI readiness assessments
- Integrate CARE Principles into data governance policies in addition to FAIR principles, particularly for Indigenous and community-owned data, ensuring ethical reuse and appropriate consent
- Clarify ownership and licensing of AI-generated content, through adoption of machine-readable provenance standards such as *C2PA*⁴⁴ and *Creative Commons Signals*

⁴⁴ <https://c2pa.org/>

5.8 Agreement on AI Regulation Is Unanimous, Implementation Fragmented and Playing Catch-up

Across all roundtable sessions, there was widespread consensus on the need for robust regulation of AI, especially in high-impact areas like research, healthcare, education, and public services. However, participants emphasised that while agreement on principles is growing, implementation remains fragmented, inconsistent, and often outpaced by technological development.

Breakout and plenary discussions consistently identified a “trust versus speed” dilemma. Regulatory efforts such as laws, frameworks and standards, including the EU AI Act, UNESCO’s AI Ethics Guidelines, OECD AI principles and ISO/IEC 42001, were praised as critical starting points. Yet, participants noted that regulatory enforcement lags behind both commercial innovation and research applications.

Several regional discrepancies emerged. For example, Australia and New Zealand currently operate under principle-based AI governance (e.g. privacy law, consumer protection), while jurisdictions like Canada and the U.S. are still debating federal alignment. In contrast, the European Union was seen as a front-runner, with implementation roadmaps already underway. However, even within the EU, AI act implementation is delayed by lack of progress in standards for data and AI conformity assessment. Participants also warned that national-level preparedness remains uneven, and many research-performing institutions still lack the capacity to navigate forthcoming requirements.

Fragmentation also extends to tools and metrics. Despite the availability of certification frameworks, policy templates, and regulatory sandboxes, few institutions reported using them systematically.

As one discussion concluded, *“We’ve stopped arguing over whether AI should be regulated. The real question is how to coordinate and scale that regulation meaningfully.”*

RECOMMENDATION: ALIGN ON GLOBAL STANDARDS AND ACCELERATE INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

To close the gap between agreement and implementation, governments, institutions, and multilateral organisations should:

- Harmonise and operationalise regulatory framework adherence (e.g. EU AI Act, UNESCO, OECD,) with international standards (e.g. ISO, IEEE, NIST)
- Develop public–private regulatory sandboxes for real-world implementation and early feedback from diverse actors, including SMEs
- Coordinate through global research communities and other multistakeholder forums, which offer more agile and dynamic spaces to support continuous global dialogue, co-creation, and adaptation of AI governance practices
- Governments should support and adopt initiatives like **AI Pact**⁴⁵ (EU, signatories include Microsoft, Google, IBM, TikTok) that enable proactive engagement with technology firms to anticipate, monitor, and mitigate emerging AI risks.

6. Final Reflection

This white paper captures a timely and globally informed reflection on the evolving relationship between data, AI, and research practice. It brings together perspectives from leading voices across sectors and regions to surface not only what is technically needed for AI to support research, but what is socially essential for that support to be responsible, inclusive, and sustainable.

Rather than treating AI as a purely technical frontier, the findings emphasise the foundational role of data readiness, the value of human agency, and the importance of embedding ethical, reproducible, and domain-sensitive practices from the outset. From the call for small models trained on meaningful data, to the recognition of infrastructure gaps and regulatory fragmentation, this report offers directions of priorities and researchers needs for stakeholders involved in higher education and research ecosystems.

We hope this work serves as a useful reference for policymakers, researchers, and technologists alike, not only to guide technical investment, but also to foster the trust, governance, and public–private collaboration in the rapidly evolving landscape of AI in research.

To contribute to this ongoing dialogue or share feedback, please contact the representatives from RDA and Microsoft. Contact details are **RDA contacts:** connie.clare@rda-foundation.org, hilary.hanahoe@rda-foundation.org | **Microsoft:** If

⁴⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-pact>

you are interested in engaging with Microsoft please reach out to:
mcollinson@microsoft.com

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank all the speakers and participants whose insights were central to this white paper. Their thoughtful contributions shaped the discussions and helped surface the core challenges and priorities around data and AI in research.

This initiative was made possible by the joint vision of Hilary Hanahoe (RDA) and Marcy Collinson (Microsoft), who led the idea and set it in motion. Together with Rachel Chiang from Microsoft, and Connie Clare from the RDA, we curated the sessions, brought together global speakers, and delivered the events in record time.

I am further grateful to Connie Clare and Rosie Allison for their support in refining the paper. Rosie also provided production and communication support to ensure timely delivery of outputs at each stage.

Sincere thanks as well to my RDA colleagues Bridget Walker, Irina Hope, and Trish Radotic for their steady direct and indirect support throughout.

About the Research Data Alliance

The [Research Data Alliance](#) (RDA) was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the vision that researchers and innovators can openly share and re-use data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society.

The RDA's mission is to build the social and technical bridges that enable that vision, accomplished through the creation, adoption and use of the social, organisational, and technical infrastructure needed to reduce barriers to data sharing and exchange. Scientists & researchers join forces with technical experts in focused Working Groups, exploratory Interest Groups and Communities of Practice. As of June 2025, the RDA is a 15000+ member strong community spread across the globe.

Everyone is welcome to join the RDA as an individual member free of charge. If you're interested in getting involved at the organisational level, please explore our [membership options](#).

About Microsoft

Microsoft Corporation is a multinational American technology company recognised for shaping the evolution of personal and enterprise computing. Founded in 1975 and headquartered in Redmond, Washington, the company initially revolutionised software accessibility through its early operating systems. Over the decades, Microsoft expanded its portfolio to encompass a broad spectrum of technologies, including productivity software, cloud infrastructure, gaming, Artificial Intelligence and Quantum Computing. With a longstanding emphasis on innovation and digital transformation, Microsoft continues to play a pivotal role in defining the future of the tech industry.

Disclaimer: This white paper is a collaborative effort between the Research Data Alliance and Microsoft, with contributions from participants of both organisations who did not receive any compensation for their involvement. AI tools were used as writing assistance for editing, language refinement, and coding support during the preparation of this document. All quotes and statements attributed to speakers and participants have been directly verified using transcripts and video recordings. Attribution has been made only with explicit consent, and general discussion quotes, although anonymised, have also been validated against recordings. Attributed quotes were shared with their respective speakers for review and commentary prior to publication. Graphs included in this paper were generated by the author, while other graphics were provided by the speakers, all of which have been cleared for use. Any substantial claims presented in this paper are supported by expert speaker statements as well as footnote citations from referenced sources, all verified by the author.

Appendix A: Keynotes Speaker Bios

Arnaud Ceol, Technical Project Manager, ICSC Foundation, Bologna, Italy

Arnaud Ceol is the Technical Project Manager of the ICSC Foundation, Italy's National Center for Research on High-Performance Computing, Big Data, and Quantum Computing. In his current role, he focuses on providing data-related services for the foundation's projects, such as IT4LIA, the Italian AI Factory, EUSAiR, a European initiative aimed at supporting the implementation of AI regulatory sandboxes, or INNOVATE, the first industrial supercomputer of the European EURO HPC infrastructure. Before ICSC, Arnaud managed bioinformatics platforms at the European Institute of Oncology in Milan and for Italy's largest oncology network, *Alleanza Contro il Cancro*. He previously contributed to the development and management of international data repositories, and standards for the representation and exchange of biological data.

Reyna Jenkyns, Associate Director, World Data System International Technology Office, Victoria, Canada

Reyna Jenkyns is currently the Associate Director for the World Data System International Technology Office, hosted at Ocean Networks Canada at the University of Victoria. Prior to the WDS, she worked for Ocean Networks Canada from 2009 to 2023. For over a decade, she managed the Data Stewardship team which provides metadata and data management, geospatial services, and expedition support. Throughout her time at ONC, she was an avid contributor to its data repository infrastructure and to the broader research data management community. From 2018 to 2024, she served on the Board of the CoreTrustSeal, the organization that provides certification for data repositories. She received her Bachelor of Mathematics from the University of Waterloo, and her Master of Science in Ocean Physics at the University of Victoria.

Kyong-Ha Lee, Director of the Hyper-scale AI Research Center at KISTI, Daejeon, South Korea

Dr. Kyong-Ha Lee received his bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees from Chungnam National University in South Korea. He then served as a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Arizona in the United States and as a senior researcher at ETRI. Currently, he is serving as the Director of the Hyper-scale AI Research Center at KISTI. He is also a lifetime member of the Korean Institute of Information Scientists and Engineers (KIISE) and the Korea Information Processing Society (KIPS), and has served as a board director for both organizations. In addition, he is a member of the AI Committee of the Korean Federation of Science and Technology Societies (KOFST) and serves on the Subcommittee for National Defense Technology Strategy under the Ministry of Science and ICT of Korea.

Harshad Kesar, Data and AI Evangelist (Higher Education), Microsoft, London, United Kingdom

Harshad is the Data & AI Evangelist with 17+ years of consulting experience in Data Analytics & Integration. He is the Data & AI lead at Microsoft UK covering Higher Education, Health & Research and passionate about Empowering organisations to achieve more with the help of technology.

Mukkesh Kumar, Head of Data Management Platform, A*STAR, Singapore

Dr Mukkesh Kumar is the Head of Data Management Platform at A*STAR, leading the Multi-modal Data Management, Data Curation & Data Stewardship, Healthcare Data Analytics & Reporting and Healthcare Software Development teams. Dr Mukkesh Kumar is a PhD alumnus of the NUS Saw Swee Hock School of Public Health, his interests are in developing generative AI and agentic solutions for biomedical informatics. Forging collaborations with the National University Hospital (NUH) in Value-based Healthcare Strategy, the Early Screening for Gestational Diabetes Mellitus in a Low Risk Population (EaGeR) pilot study conducted at NUH for the real world deployment of early pregnancy GDM predictor AI model. Working in close partnership with Singapore's Ministry of Health (MOH), Dr Mukkesh Kumar is shaping the national data standardization and standardized data analytics strategies. Dr Mukkesh Kumar has been mentoring the Data Managers at US Boston Children's Hospital/Harvard Medical School for multi-centre clinical research studies, building talent and capabilities in the global research ecosystem.

Haritha Thilakarathne, Cloud Solution Architect (AI), Microsoft, Sydney, Australia

Dr. Haritha Thilakarathne is a Cloud Solution Architect in AI at Microsoft, specialising in scalable, secure, and intelligent cloud architectures on Azure, with experience in machine learning and deep learning. He was awarded as a Microsoft Most Valuable Professional in AI for 8 times. Haritha holds a Ph.D. in Deep Learning and actively contributes to the technical community through conferences, meetups, and his blog.

Appendix B: Contributing Participants

We extend our sincere thanks to all participants for their enthusiasm, expertise, and insightful contributions to the roundtable discussions. We gratefully acknowledge them as key contributors to the findings of this whitepaper.

Please note that only participants who provided consent have been included in the list.

2025, May 13 Session Contributors

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Reyna	Jenkyns	Director	World Data System	Canada
Arnaud	Ceol	Technical Project Manager	ICSC	Italy
Harshad	Keskar	Data and AI Evangelist	Microsoft	UK
Martina	Stockhause	Data Management	DKRZ / IPCC DDC	Germany
Daniela	Santos Oliveira	Program Manager	WDS	USA
Amy	Nurnberger	Program Head, Data Management Services	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA
Louise	Bezuidenhout	Senior researcher	Leiden University	Netherlands
Daniela	Hensen	Senior Portfolio Manager for AI	BBSRC	UK
Jaime	Combariza	Executive Director PARCC	University of Pennsylvania	USA
Natalie	Meyers	AI Researcher in Residence	Association of Research Libraries	USA
Daniel	Goroff	Vice President and Program Director	Alfred P. Sloan Foundation	USA
Solomon	Gizaw	Assistant Professor	Addis Ababa University	Ethiopia
Hannah	Hope	Open Research Lead	Wellcome	UK
Lee	Wilson	Director of RDM	Digital Research Alliance of Canada	Canada
Ryan	Scherle	Head of Platform Development	Dryad Data Repository	USA
Traci	Snowden	Product Manager - Digital Commons	Elsevier	USA

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
		Data/Mendeley Data/GREI PI		
Gavin	Farrell	PhD Candidate - ML Best Practices (Life Sciences)	University of Padova	Italy
Maria	Mirza	Scientific Project Manager	Euro-Biolmaging ERIC	Germany
Vincent	Zimmer	Principal Software Engineer	Engineering	USA
Ayanna	Dawkins	Account Executive	Microsoft	USA
Marco	Rorro	AI Solutions Architect	EGI Foundation	Italy
Alex	Delipalta	Director	RDA Europe	Ireland
Whitney	Stewart	Cloud Specialist	Microsoft	United States
Wolmar	Nyberg Åkerström	Bioinformatician / Data steward	ELIXIR Sweden; NBIS - National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden, Science for Life Laboratory (SciLifeLab) Sweden, Uppsala University	Sweden
Didier	Chalon	Information Architecture	UCB	Belgium
Gabriela	Pino	Academica advisor for research	Universidad Nacional	Costa Rica
Emil	Traicu	Architect	concordia	Canada
Giulia Raffaella	De Luca	PhD student	University of Bologna	Italy
Andrea	Cristofori	Data Solution Architect	EGI.eu	Netherlands
David	Lifka	Consultant	Microsoft ISD	USA
Connie	Clare	Community Development Manager	RDA	United Kingdom
Marcy	Collinson	Director, Worldwide Academic Research	Microsoft	USA
Rachel	Chiang	Product Marketing manager	Microsoft	USA

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Shalini	Kurapati	Community Engagement (RDA)/ Co-founder (Clearbox)	RDA/ Clearbox AI	Italy
Rosie	Allison	Communication Specialist	RDA	Belgium
Hilary	Hanahoe	Secretary General	RDA	Italy

2025, May 15 Session Contributors

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Kyon-ha	Lee	AI Director	KISTI	South Korea
Haritha	Thilakarathne	Cloud AI Architect	Microsoft	Australia
Mukkesh	Kumar	Head of Data Management	A*Star	Singapore
Michelle	Barker	Director	ReSA	Australia
Pascal	Elahi	Quantum Lead	Pawsey Supercomputing Centre	Australia
Andrew	Mair	AI Lead	Bendigo Kangan Institute	Australia
Gnana	Bharathy	Research Data Specialist (AI/ ML, Architecture)	ARDC	Australia
Andrew	Treloar	Director, International Strategy	Australian Research Data Commons	Australia
Daksh	Mehta	Research intern	Indian institute of Science	India
Amir	Aryani	A/Prof Social Data Analytics	Swinburne University of Technology	Australia
Kavana	D Rajan	Support Engineer - AI services	Microsoft	India
Sajani	Perera	PhD Candidate	Griffith University	Australia

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Mingfang	Wu	Product Manager	Australian Research Data Commons	Australia
Rob	Smith	Industry Advisor	Microsoft	Singapore
James	Savage	Research Manager	Southern Institute of Technology Te Pūkenga	New Zealand
Priyanka	Nair-Turkich	Research Data Specialist	The University of Melbourne	Australia
Catherine	Ennis	Future Ready Skills Specialist	Microsoft	Australia
Nicola	Fiore	Software Architect	EGI FOUNDATION	Italy
Trish	Radotic	RDA Regional Community Manager (Oceania and East Asia)	Australian Research Data Commons / Research Data Alliance	Australia
Moji	Ghadimi	Head of AI and Quantum Algorithms	QCIF	Australia
Daochang	Liu	Lecturer	UWA	Australia
Mohamed	Drira	Associate Professor and Governor	Saint Mary's University	Canada
Emily	Barker	Senior High Performance Computing Engineer	University of Western Australia	Australia
Linda	McIver	Executive Director	Australian Data Science Education Institute	Australia
Shalini	Kurapati	Community Engagement (RDA)/ Co-founder (Clearbox)	RDA/ Clearbox AI	Italy

Name	Surname	Role	Organisation	Country
Connie	Clare	Community Development Manager	RDA	UK
Rosie	Allison	Communication Specialist	RDA	Belgium
Hilary	Hanahoe	Secretary General	RDA	Italy

Appendix C: Breakout Room Discussion Summaries

Breakout Room (May 13)	Data Readiness (🌱 / 🌱 / 🌱)	AI in Research (🌱 / 🌱 / 🌱)	AI Governance (🌱 / 🌱 / 🌱)
Frontiers	<p>🌱 Growing awareness of what constitutes AI-readiness, with FAIR principles gaining traction and increased use of open data repositories.</p> <p>🌱 Retrofitting legacy data is costly and labour-intensive; widespread absence of common schemas, metadata standards, and consistent credit systems.</p> <p>🌱 AI tools for automated metadata generation, schema</p>	<p>🌱 AI proves effective in managing growing complexity in multimodal research datasets; examples include agentic AI for clinical trial navigation.</p> <p>🌱 Issues with reproducibility, poor documentation, data bias, and proliferation of low-quality AI outputs.</p> <p>🌱 Small, domain-specific models are gaining momentum; shared frameworks like the Model Openness</p>	<p>🌱 UNESCO-led frameworks⁴⁷ and institutional-level policies are emerging; advances in deidentification tools.</p> <p>🌱 Difficulty reconciling privacy and openness; fragmented governance makes operationalisation challenging.</p> <p>🌱 Infrastructure-level solutions like MLOps and Trusted Research</p>

⁴⁷ <https://www.unesco.org/ethics-ai/en>

Breakout Room (May 13)	Data Readiness (🌸 / 🌱 / 🌿)	AI in Research (🌸 / 🌱 / 🌿)	AI Governance (🌸 / 🌱 / 🌿)
	inference; FAIR implementation profiles tailored for AI pipelines emerging (e.g., Croissant, Datasheets).	Framework (MOF) ⁴⁶ are tackling reproducibility with documentation standards.	Environments (TREs) are helping embed governance into workflows.
Horizons	<p>🌸 Strong healthcare foundations (e.g., NHS); FAIR principles seen as adaptable globally.</p> <p>🌿 Regional infrastructure inequality and bureaucratic resistance to updating protocols.</p> <p>🌱 Scenario planning toolkits (e.g., AI Futures Planning Toolkit) and adoption of standards like HL7 FHIR and SNOMED CT support responsible expansion.</p>	<p>🌸 AI enables discovery in high-complexity domains; boosts productivity in lab/clinical research.</p> <p>🌿 Tension between commercial tools and open science needs; reproducibility still a concern.</p> <p>🌱 Futurescapes and other foresight methods allow strategic planning for AI in research ecosystems.</p>	<p>🌸 National policy pilots and active engagement with international regulatory discussions.</p> <p>🌿 Healthcare-specific governance still fragmented; lack of cross-border standardisation.</p> <p>🌱 Ethical use of synthetic data and digital twins explored as testbeds for regulation.</p>
Pathways	<p>🌸 Advances in standardised APIs and improved mechanisms for dataset discovery.</p> <p>🌿 Metadata gaps, incomplete provenance records, and inconsistent</p>	<p>🌸 Improved tooling for researcher workflows, particularly for reporting and data management.</p> <p>🌿 Lack of structured documentation practices; difficulties</p>	<p>🌸 Local institutional frameworks being established.</p> <p>🌿 Translating governance principles into practice is difficult</p>

⁴⁶ <https://isitopen.ai/>

Breakout Room (May 13)	Data Readiness (🌹 / 🌱 / 🌿)	AI in Research (🌹 / 🌱 / 🌿)	AI Governance (🌹 / 🌱 / 🌿)
	<p>licensing.</p> <p>🌱 Use of AI for metadata enrichment, Quality Control, and Creative Commons-style attribution systems in development.</p>	<p>standardising model-sharing.</p> <p>🌱 Integration of specialised AI tools into Virtual Research Environments and reproducible ML pipelines.</p>	<p>without integrated tooling.</p> <p>🌱 Dashboards and sandboxes under development to operationalise compliance in active research environments.</p>
Plenary	<p>🌹 Progress in creating interoperable tools and awareness-raising through training and community engagement.</p> <p>🌿 Challenges of operationalising frameworks in smaller or under-resourced institutions; cost remains a blocker.</p> <p>🌱 Lightweight infrastructures and FAIR-aligned resources tailored to research environments with limited capacity.</p>	<p>🌹 Rapid AI-driven modelling advancements across disciplines.</p> <p>🌿 Gaps in model trustworthiness and evaluation capacity; limited explainability.</p> <p>🌱 Templates and shared evaluation frameworks under development for modular AI systems.</p>	<p>🌹 Some universities trialling formal AI codes of practice.</p> <p>🌿 Governance fatigue and uneven implementation at the institutional level.</p> <p>🌱 Collaborative frameworks and incentives for shared compliance measures are emerging.</p>

Table 1: Summaries of the breakout room discussions on 2025, May 13

Legend: (🌹 Rose (Successes/Opportunities) / 🌿 Thorn(Challenges) 🌱 Bud (Potential))

Breakout Room (May 15)	Data Readiness (🌹 / 🌱 / 🌿)	AI in Research (🌹 / 🌱)	AI Governance (🌹 / 🌱)
Horizons	<p>🌹 Established standards and ethical frameworks gaining traction.</p> <p>🌱 Inconsistent benchmarking and persistent issues with data consent and contextual repurposing.</p> <p>🌿 Movement toward inclusive, explainable small models, especially suited for global and resource-limited environments.</p>	<p>🌹 AI enables biomedical innovation and complex research simulations.</p> <p>🌱 Reproducibility and documentation lapses hinder validation.</p> <p>🌿 Emphasis on interpretability algorithms and researcher training in critical AI use.</p>	<p>🌹 Recognition of ISO 42001 , EU AI Act , and UNESCO guidelines .</p> <p>🌱 Insufficient transparency and lack of public understanding of AI implications.</p> <p>🌿 Push for interdisciplinary governance and public-facing AI education.</p>
Pathways	<p>🌹 Federated tools and SLM infrastructure improve data engineering accessibility.</p> <p>🌱 Legacy systems and poor data interoperability remain barriers.</p> <p>🌿 Increasing adoption of automated schema generation and inclusive NLP tools .</p>	<p>🌹 AI drives literature synthesis , domain-specific insights , and efficient modelling .</p> <p>🌱 Critical thinking risks from overreliance and lack of interpretability.</p> <p>🌿 Calls for balanced AI-human workflows and co-creation platforms .</p>	<p>🌹 Adoption of certification frameworks and institutional audits.</p> <p>🌱 Lack of clear boundaries for AI behaviour and inadequate regulatory coverage.</p> <p>🌿 Movement toward shared governance tooling and multi-stakeholder input.</p>

Breakout Room (May 15)	Data Readiness (🌹 / 🌿 / 🌱)	AI in Research (🌹 / 🌿 / 🌱)	AI Governance (🌹 / 🌿 / 🌱)
Plenary	<p>🌹 Cloud platforms and modular APIs enhance scalability.</p> <p>🌿 Ongoing data bias and geographic representation gaps.</p> <p>🌱 Vision for multi-lingual, FAIR-compliant, inclusive AI datasets .</p>	<p>🌹 AI expands the frontier of hypothesis testing and simulation science .</p> <p>🌿 Skills shortages and low literacy in responsible AI deployment .</p> <p>🌱 Value in developing literature-aware models and explainability-first pipelines .</p>	<p>🌹 Broader awareness of global regulatory initiatives .</p> <p>🌿 Opaque data pipelines and evaluation practices remain unchecked.</p> <p>🌱 Priority placed on auditable governance , risk frameworks , and cross-border harmoniation .</p>

Table 2: Summaries of the Breakout Discussion for the Asia and Oceania session. Legend:
 (🌹 Rose (Successes/Opportunities) / 🌿 Thorn(Challenges) 🌱 Bud (Potential))

June, 2025

